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STRATEGY FOR IMPROVING PUBLIC SERVICES CASE STUDY AT THE REGIONAL REVENUE OFFICE OF EAST KALIMANTAN PROVINCE IN SAMARINDA

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ABSTRACT

Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services, is a reference for government administrators to provide optimal and maximum services. Public services have so far been considered to be far from the expectations and desires of the community. The expected services are services that are fast, precise, easy, transparent, uncomplicated, and professional. The research aims to determine the strategy for improving public services carried out by the Regional Technical Implementation Unit (UPTD) Office of the East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service in Samarinda. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative research. The data analysis used is qualitative data analysis which begins with the process of data collection, data simplification, data presentation, and conclusion. In this research, data collection techniques using literature studies, and field studies are used, namely by collecting data through observation, documentation, and interviews to obtain clearer information on what is needed in the research. The results of the research show that: (1) the strategy to improve public services at the UPTD Office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda has gone well, namely: building service quality and improving service management, building a culture of awareness of the importance of service quality, providing parking spaces spacious, large warehouse, comfortable waiting room and place to fill out forms for customers, and installation of signboards for procedures or flow in providing services, there are information boards relating to service information; and (2) the inhibiting factor in improving public services at the UPTD Office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda, namely that there are still some employee errors in providing services, although there are no longer many.

KEYWORDS

Strategy Improvement of Public Services, East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service Office in Samarinda.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Public services are a series of activities carried out by the government and its officials for the community to improve the quality of people's lives while providing satisfaction to the people they serve. Agung Kurniawan stated in [1] that public service is the provision of services (serving) the needs of other people or the community who have an interest in the organization by the basic rules and procedures that have been determined.

In [2] the definition of public services is an activity or series of activities to fulfill service needs by statutory regulations for every citizen and resident for goods, services, and/or services. administrative services provided by public service providers.

In the implementation of public services carried out by government officials in various service aspects, including those involving the fulfillment of civil rights and basic needs of the population, it is still felt that it is not as expected by the community. This can be seen, among other things, from the number of complaints, and complaints from the public, whether conveyed directly to the leadership of the service unit or through readers' letters to various mass media. On the other hand, the community as the main element served has not provided effective control to become a driving element in efforts to improve the quality of public services.

One of the essences of good governance is the creation of an effective, efficient, and accountable service product from the government that is directed towards the community. For this reason, it is necessary to carry out various strategies to improve the quality of public services so that in the end the goal of implementing public services will be achieved and provide a level of satisfaction to the people who receive them.

However, in creating a quality service that gives satisfaction to the people who receive it, there are still many obstacles and other factors that result in public services provided by the government not being optimal.

Various efforts continue to be made by the government and its officials to improve public services. This is a strategy or effort to fully improve the quality of Indonesian people and Indonesian society as a whole.

Various strategies that can be implemented to improve public services to the community include improving the quality and professionalism of government officials, creating policies that support the implementation of improved public services to the community, issuing or creating minimum service standards, and increasing the provision of facilities that support the quality of public services. With the strategies mentioned above, it is hoped that the process of providing public services to the community can improve.

The research aims to determine the strategy for improving public services carried out by the Regional Technical Implementation Unit Office of the East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service in Samarinda.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Types of research

This research is descriptive and aims to provide an overview and explanation of strategies for improving public services at the UPTD Office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda.

2.2. Research Location

This research was conducted at the UPTD Office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda.

2.3. Data collection

The research data sources are the results of observations at the research location, informants, and various documents related to strategies for improving public services to the community and literature studies. Data collected: (1) primary data, namely data obtained from sources by conducting direct questions and answers and being guided through questions that are by the research focus prepared in advance; and (2) secondary data, namely data obtained through several sources of information, including documents and literature studies.

2.4. Data analysis

The data analysis used in this research is descriptive qualitative data analysis. As stated by [3] qualitative data analysis is a cyclical and interactive process that moves between four axes, namely data collection, data reduction, presenting data, and drawing conclusions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Vision and Mission of UPTD Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province

Vision: Realization of Optimal Regional Income to Meet Demands for Providing Regional Financing. The explanation of the keyword "vision" is as follows: (1) regional income is all regional cash receipts in a certain fiscal year period which are the rights of the region, (2) optimal is achieving satisfactory and best results, (3) meeting demands is achieving results by what has been determined or targeted, and (4) regional financing is all regional cash expenditures within a certain period.

Mission: (1) increase the professionalism of employee human resources, (2) increase public awareness of their obligation to pay taxes, levies, and other income, (3) improve the quality of excellent service that is evenly distributed and easily accessible to the public, and (4) increase optimal contribution to the East Kalimantan Province APBD.

3.2. The main tasks of the Regional Revenue Service UPTD

The main task is to carry out some operational technical activities and/or supporting technical activities for the Service in the field of Regional taxes, Regional levies, and other income as well as legal income. To carry out these main tasks, the UPTD Regional Revenue Service has the following functions: (1) preparing operational technical plans for data collection and determining regional taxes, regional levies, and other income as well as legal income, (2) Implementing operational technical policies for bookkeeping and billing regional taxes, regional levies and other income and legal income, (3) monitoring, evaluating and reporting regional taxes, regional levies, and other income and legal income, (4) management of administrative affairs, (5) development of functional position groups, and (6) carrying out other tasks assigned by the Head of Service by his duties and functions.

3.3. Organizational Structure of UPTD Regional Revenue Service

The organizational structure of the Regional Revenue Service UPTD consists of (1) the Head of the UPTD, (2) the Administration Sub-Section, (3) the Bookkeeping and Billing Section, and (4) the Functional Position Group (Source: East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service UPTD Office).

3.4. Strategy for Improving Public Services at the UPTD Office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda City

For every service that is a mandatory matter, each SKPD generally has a service procedure. However, according to developments and community demands, of course, it always needs to be

improved, including regarding cooperation between Regional Work Unit (SKPD), because government institutions are always changing. For this reason, it is necessary to reorganize service procedures and supporting systems involving SKPD and institutions outside the regional government. In refining these procedures, simplification measures were taken.

Public Service Strategy is identical to the representation of the existence of government bureaucracy because it is directly related to one of the government's functions, namely providing proper and correct services to the community. Therefore, the quality of public services is a reflection of the quality of government bureaucracy. Service is an activity where there is a provider or service provider and a service recipient, where the service provider must be able to provide services according to what the service recipient, in this case the community, desires. In terms of service, referring to the opinion of [2], where the service provider must be able to meet the needs of the party they serve directly without any intermediary so that communication can occur between those providing the service and those receiving the service.

3.4.1. Improved Service Organization

The aim of improving service organization is to ensure fast, easy, affordable, and equitable service distribution, especially in direct interaction with service users. Along with the development of technology and information, organizational problems are increasing both in terms of quantity and quality demands of service users. The types of quality demanded by society or service users are increasingly complex. This all forces the management of the institution to look again at the extent of quality that can be provided to its customers.

The institution's attention to customer quality covers various aspects, namely looking at how to build a culture of quality improvement, namely providing awareness to the human resources within it of the importance of service quality. Apart from that, attention is also needed to pay attention to these management aspects, which need to be applied in the process of running the organization. Apart from that, another important thing is the establishment of service quality standards as a guide in performance assessment.

Based on the results of interviews with S. Husein Sadly as Head of the UPTD of the East Kalimantan Provincial Revenue Service stated that: improving the organization of government apparatus services is one of the strategies in creating public services to the community, thus, we can improve complaints that come from the public who think that services are still inadequate. again (interview, 17 December 2014)

In the past, the public service paradigm gave a very large role to the government as the sole provider, the role of parties outside the government never had a place. The public and the private world only have a small role in providing public services. To find out the quality of service that is felt by consumers, there are indicators measuring consumer satisfaction which lie in five dimensions of service quality according to what consumers say.

Then it was said that Mr H.E.A. Robyan Syachrial as Head of Administrative Subdivision that the next step as one of the strategies for improving public service organizations is to create policies that support the implementation of improving public services to the community, in this way, it is hoped that the publication of policies regarding improving public service organizations will encourage creating quality services that are effective, efficient and accountable" (interview, 17 December 2014).

Furthermore, Mr. Solhan Zubaidy as Head of the Bookkeeping Section stated that apart from that, one of the aims of making the policy was also to change the image of public services which tend to be complicated, wasteful, and take a long time, so that in the end Later, the community will feel increasingly satisfied with every service provided by UPTD, so that it can increase regional income (interview, 17 December 2014).

Then added by S. Husein Sadly as Head of the UPTD Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province, added that apart from improving the services of public service organizations, one other aspect that the UPTD of Samarinda City needs to pay attention to to improve public service organizations is increasing the provision of facilities. support the quality of public services, because, without being supported by the availability of complete facilities, it will hamper the process of providing public services to the community (interview, 17 December 2014).

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be stated that the UPTD Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province has improved the organization of public services and the professionalism of government officials, one of which is the strategy for creating good public services for the community.

Based on the results of observations made, the UPTD service of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province has provided good service for the community and in addition has also provided physical facilities in the form of a large parking area, a large warehouse, a comfortable waiting room and a place to fill out forms for the customer. The provision of facilities and infrastructure is by the opinion of [7] that managing evidence of service quality is done by complementing service facilities and infrastructure. The provision of facilities and infrastructure is also to the opinion of Parasuraman, Berry, and Zeithaml in [8] that the quality dimension is in the form of tangibles/direct evidence, namely the completeness of services that can be seen/felt directly by the community as service users.

3.4.2. Increased Improvement of Service Procedures

By [4] concerning Guidelines for Providing One-Stop Integrated Services. The establishment of a one-stop integrated service aims to simplify service procedures so that it can make it easier for the public to process permits.

In this regard, the principle is lean but rich in function, and placing reliable employees in every field. Before institutional restructuring is carried out, the first step that must be taken is deregulation, by reviewing and improving the laws and regulations that underlie the delivery of services in various Regional Government Agencies to be more adapted to reform aspirations by cutting down various regulations that hinder them to make them simpler/more efficient and shorten long bureaucratic routes for ease and smooth service implementation. This effort includes, among other things, establishing various service standards, and simplifying institutions and spans of control. The preparation of this SOP is also by what was proposed by [5], namely a strategy for developing or simplifying procedural systems. The procedural system regulates the stages of service in detail, so this procedural system is often the source of the cause of the service system becoming convoluted, rigid, inefficient, and ineffective. Then [6] stated that one strategy to improve the quality of public services is with Customer Strategy, namely by creating simple procedures, and a pleasant and soothing office environment. The next step to improve the quality of public services is to increase the professionalism of public service officials.

Based on the results of interviews with S. Husein Sadly as Head of the East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service UPTD stated that efforts to improve public service procedures can also be carried out through corporatization of public service units. Management autonomy policy (corporatization), namely the granting of explicit and clear authority to certain units/work units of Government Agencies to carry out operational management of services independently and autonomously." (interview, 18 December 2014).

The same thing was also stated by Mr. Solhan Zubaidy Head of the Bookkeeping Section, that this policy is intended to develop and improve the performance of government organizational units, so that they can provide excellent service and choose excellence, especially for work units that carry out

community service functions. (interview, 18 December 2014). Furthermore, it was stated by Mr. H.E.A. Robyan Syachrial as Head of Administration Subdivision that this corporatization step must of course be followed by various changes and adjustments to the systems and management of these service units, Quality Improvement Efforts including changes in the values and work culture of the organizers (interview, 18 December 2014).

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be stated that the regional government has and is currently preparing various service standards. With standards, it is possible to measure the performance of the services provided. Service standards are provisions for the shape, size, and guidelines of general services carried out according to the service sector. This means that service providers have the right to determine the type and quality of services based on the authority and capabilities of their respective regions. In this way, service standards can be a tool to increase the accountability of service providers towards the community.

3.4.3. Improving the Quality of Service Provider Personnel

Service quality becomes important when an organization has problems related to demands for service quality and complaints from service users. Apart from that, as the number of similar institutions increases, there is competition in providing these services, which also gives a signal to institutions to improve services to other parties.

Efforts to improve service quality and awareness to develop the organization through various aspects, namely product quality, packaging, facilities, and infrastructure, as well as the quality of human resources. The application of this strategy is by the opinion of [9] that organizational culture is an organizational value system and will influence the way work is carried out and the way employees behave. Furthermore, it was stated by [5] that cultural development is closely related to the process of changing the character of service personnel based on their outlook on life, norms, and habits which are reflected in their behavior in providing services to the community.

Based on the results of interviews with S. Husein Sadly as Head of the UPTD Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province stated that what I do to improve the quality of service provider personnel is to improve human resources, because that is an aspect that should be considered in efforts to improve public services (interview, 19 December 2014).

Then Mr. H.E.A. Robyan Syachrial as Head of the Administration Subdivision said that apart from that, to improve the quality of service delivery personnel, a good attitude and mentality is needed from every government apparatus who directly deals with the community (interview, 19 December 2014). Furthermore, Mr. Solhan Zubaidy as Head of the Bookkeeping Section stated that when talking about the quality of employees in the UPTD office, I think it is good, but quality needs to be improved through training (interview, 19 December 2014).

Based on the results of research and observations that have been carried out in the field, it can be stated that efforts to develop the organization must always be pursued by the leadership, namely by building service quality and improving service management. Building a culture to raise awareness of the importance of service quality must be attached to all human resources in the organization.

If the principles in building service management and attention to the factors that influence the level of quality are paid attention to and applied in the service process, it will provide customer satisfaction. Apart from that, it is important to pay attention to the existence of service quality standards which are a measure/benchmark in assessing the quality of public services at the Samarinda City UPTD office.

3.4.4. Inhibiting Factors for the Strategy for Improving Public Services at the UPTD Office of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda City.

In general, the obstacle to strategies for improving public services at the UPTD Office of the East Kalimantan Province Regional Revenue Service in Samarinda is the quality of employee performance in providing services (professional work). As stated by [10] professionalism is reliability and expertise in carrying out tasks so that they are carried out with high quality, on time, carefully, and with procedures that are easy for customers to understand and follow.

Work quality is one way to determine employee performance, namely the employee's ability to complete work with good quality. The quality of an employee's work can be seen from the neatness and thoroughness in carrying out their duties or the level of errors made by employees in carrying out or carrying out a task or job.

The following are the results of an interview with S. Husein Sadly Head of the UPTD Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province stated that when talking about the quality of employee performance, mistakes in work do exist, but in terms of number or quantity they do not have an overall effect. This is because of the coaching through supervision carried out by the Management for employees (interview, 19 December 2014).

Then the results of the interview with H.E.A. Robyan Syachrial as Head of Administration Subdivision stated that if we look at the level of cleanliness and tidiness of employees in carrying out their work, it is relatively clean and neat because the work results are mostly in the form of administration which requires cleanliness and neatness (interview, 19 December 2014)

Furthermore, the results of an interview with Mr. Solhan Zubaidy Head of the Bookkeeping Section stated that in carrying out their work, employees always adhere to existing regulations, instructions, and procedures that have been outlined to achieve the expected performance results and avoid deviations (interview, 19 December 2014).

Based on the results of observations and interviews that have been conducted regarding the Strategy for Improving Public Services, in this case, the quality of employee performance in terms of work accuracy or the level of work errors, there are not too many errors occurring, leaders often urge and provide direction to employees to be careful in their work.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, conclusions can be drawn, namely:

1. The strategy to improve public services at the office of the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda has been going well, namely: (1) building service quality and improving service management, building a culture of awareness of the importance of service quality, (2) providing parking spaces spacious, large warehouse, comfortable waiting room and place to fill out forms for customers, and (3) installation of signboards for procedures or flow in providing services, the presence of information boards relating to service information.
2. The inhibiting factor in improving public services at the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda is that there are still some employee errors in providing services, although there are no longer many.

4.2. Suggestion

The suggestions are as follows:

1. To be more adapted to the aspirations of bureaucratic reform by cutting various rules that are less simple to make them simpler or more efficient by shortening service bureaucratic routes for ease and smoothness of service implementation.
2. It would be better if the Regional Revenue Service of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda further improves the quality of service towards improving the quality of service and awareness to develop the organization through various aspects, starting from attention to service quality, providing information, quality of human resources, and accountability for change. which mean.

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